

UNIVERSITY WEST

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

Sweden is generally considered a strong case in relation to gender equality policy in general and for policies on gender-based violence (GBV) specifically. From a policy perspective, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, and reprisals in the workplace (including academic organisations and in relation to students) have been regarded as forms of discrimination and as such are regulated through the Swedish Discrimination Act (in addition to such violations that are regulated in the penal code). The obligation to apply preventive measures, regularly examine risks, undertake measures, and remedy or take action against suspected cases is regulated in law and includes an obligation for employers and education providers to collaborate with employee and student representatives. This means that all HEIs in Sweden at the institutional level are bound by the law to work to prevent and to handle cases. HEIs are also obligated to work against victimisation and workplace bullying and to prevent and handle threats, crises, and emergency situations through the Work Environment Act. Through the government mission on gender mainstreaming (JIHU¹), all HEIs are furthermore obligated to work with gender mainstreaming in order to realise Sweden's overarching gender equality objectives, one of which is: 'Men's violence against women must stop. Women and men, girls and boys must have the same rights and opportunities to physical integrity.' There are also general protections for human rights advocates that aim to prevent the harassment of those who actively work to promote human rights more generally and there is a comprehensive penal code in which GBV is addressed (see the country report for Sweden, Callerstig 2021).

There is no exact information on how many HEIs have policies and guidelines on sexual harassment, even though, according to the law, all of them should. An investigation into compliance with the Discrimination Act and with the requirement to apply active anti-discrimination measures at Swedish HEIs was conducted by the Swedish Equality Ombudsman in 2019-2021.

¹ JIHU=Jämställdhetsintegrering i högskolor och universitet in English GMA Gender mainstreaming in Academia, see Country Report Sweden: <https://zenodo.org/record/5534004#.YeqlwvjTVD8>

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

University West has a set of three policies addressing gender-based violence (GBV):

- 1) Strategy for Sustainable Development 2021-2023 (hereafter called 'the Strategy'. This Strategy is a more general document addressing GBV among other priorities. It includes the plan for the university's gender mainstreaming work.)
- 2) Guidelines for University West's Work to Prevent and Act against Discrimination and Bullying/Victimisation (hereafter called 'the Guidelines').
- 3) Procedure in Cases of Discrimination, Harassment, Sexual Harassment, and Retaliation (hereafter called 'the Procedure').

The rector has the primary responsibility for the university's work environment, which includes ensuring equal opportunities and equal treatment and counteracting and dealing with discrimination (Lika villkor). Heads of department, university director, the library director, and department heads of work units have direct responsibility for the work environment within their respective departments (delegated from the rector) to prevent discrimination and victimisation/bullying. Responsible managers also have the obligation to investigate and take action in cases of suspicion of sexual harassment and harassment. There is one coordinator for Lika villkor (Equal Opportunities/Treatment) and one for gender mainstreaming. Every employee and student at University West is also individually responsible for preventing discrimination and bullying/victimisation in everyday interactions with colleagues, students, and employees at the university. The Sustainability Council is a collaboration platform for supporting the strategic management of sustainability work with associated projects/working groups. The Council is led by the pro-rector and consists of representatives of work units, the Research and Education Committee, the Student Union, employee organisations, and the coordinators for social and ecological/economic sustainability. Its mission includes:

- a) advancing the strategic sustainability work within the university;
- b) advising the rector and the university's management team;
- c) coordinating the overall analysis and follow-up of the university's sustainability work and developing proposals for development areas and updates in the sustainability strategy.

The gender mainstreaming mission (JIHU) is included in the university's sustainability work and is also a platform for networking, sharing ideas, and giving support to departments and institutions.

URLs

- › Strategy for Sustainable Development 2021-2023: <https://www.hv.se/om-oss/vision-strategier-och-satsningar/hallbar-utveckling/sa-har-jobbar-vi-med-hallbarhet/>
- › Guidelines for University West's Work to Prevent and Act against Discrimination and Bullying/Victimisation: <https://www.hv.se/globalassets/dokument/riktlinjer-for-hogskolan-vasts-arbete-for-att-forebygga-och-atgarda-diskriminering-samt-krankande-sarbehandling-2018-175-a21.pdf>
- › Procedure in Cases of Discrimination, Harassment, Sexual Harassment, and Retaliation: <https://www.hv.se/globalassets/dokument/rutin-vid-diskriminering-trakasserier-sexuella-trakasserier-och-repressalier-2018-185-a21.pdf>

Entry into force: The Guidelines and the Procedure entered into force in 2018 and the Strategy in 2021.

TRAINING

The university has set up information and training initiatives in connection with Lika Villkor (Equal Opportunities/Treatment) and JIHU (gender mainstreaming). It has been carried out annually since 2016/17. The purpose is to provide information on current legislation and increase knowledge and awareness of formal and informal processes of discrimination in order to promote social inclusion and equal opportunities/treatment. It is addressed at all categories of employees, including doctoral students, as well as students who began their programme of study during these years.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

There are elements in specific courses and education programmes, such as social pedagogy and social psychiatric care. In the child and adolescent studies field of research, there are also research projects, outreach activities, and seminars that address issues of GBV.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The three policies address the same following **five** forms of GBV: psychological violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, and economic and financial violence.

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The three policies combined cover all **7Ps**. While all policies address prevention and partnership, the Strategy is the only policy that addresses prevalence, and the Procedure is the only policy that addresses protection and policy. Both the Guidelines and the Procedure address prosecution and provision of services.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups

Strategy

Academic and non-academic staff

Guidelines

Academic staff, non-academic staff, students, and others

Procedure

Academic staff, non-academic staff, students, and others

The three policies combined address all target groups. The Strategy is the only policy that is solely focused on academic and non-academic staff. The other two policies address all groups and identify other groups as well, such as people who do not have a direct employment relationship to the university, i.e. hired staff, fellows, trainees, and people on parental leave. The document is also aimed at everyone who studies at University West as well as applicants and people looking for education or work at the university (for vacancies and educations / courses).

Intersectionality addressed: Yes. The Strategy for Sustainable Development 2021-2023 addresses intersectionality; it does so implicitly in its reasoning about different types of inequalities and also explicitly in relation to sustainability work at the university, stating that '[w]orking with gender mainstreaming within the

framework of Agenda 2030 means applying a gender equality analysis to the entire agenda in order to identify the gender equality problems that stand in the way of achieving sustainable development and the goals in the agenda. This means not just working with goal 5, which is explicitly about gender equality, but also highlighting gender equality problems in the various goals and sub-goals in the agenda that we as a university and authority are affected by. In order to create an accurate analysis of our inequality problems and the need for action, we need to understand that inequality is something that affects people and groups differently. Therefore, we need an analysis and a break that is based on more power structures than just gender (e.g. ethnicity, socio-economics / class and age). For this reason, the interpretation of gender equality used in gender equality integration work at Swedish universities is well adapted to Agenda 2030. Lack of gender equality is still in focus, but is viewed consistently through an intersectional perspective. This means focusing and analysing on how gender interacts with other social power structures, such as ethnicity, race, class, age, sexuality, and functionality, in order to obtain a more complex and contextual understanding of concrete obstacles to achieving social sustainability.' (p. 27)

Specific vulnerable groups: The three policies combined address **all vulnerable groups** defined in UniSAFE mapping as well as other groups. These include international students and staff, early-career researchers, staff and students with disabilities, staff and students with migrant and ethnic minority backgrounds,

LGBTQIA+ staff and students, staff with temporary contracts, new and expectant mothers. The Guidelines address all defined vulnerable groups and identify other vulnerable groups such as

people who have an employment or student relationship with the university. The Procedure addresses all defined vulnerable groups but does not identify any other groups. The Strategy addresses all defined vulnerable groups except international staff and students and new and expectant mothers.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. The Guidelines and the Procedure both address the role of bystanders. The Guidelines policy reads: 'Furthermore, each employee and student at University West has the responsibility to prevent discrimination and abusive discrimination in their everyday interactions with colleagues, students, staff, and applicants to the university. This is done by respectfully treating each other and working for an environment free from discrimination, harassment, sexual harassment, and abusive discrimination. By pointing out any irregularities that come to your attention, you take responsibility for this.' The Procedure reads: 'If you witness someone else being subject to harassment or discrimination, you should talk to your immediate manager about the situation (employee) or to the department head / responsible teacher (student). If it is the manager / responsible teacher who is involved, you can instead talk to the HR department, the manager's manager (employee), the teacher's manager (student), or a union / student union representative. If you hear from a colleague that he or she feels vulnerable, give him or her the support you can give and encourage the person to inform their manager about the situation.'

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes. The Procedure addresses the role of (alleged) perpetrators. It mentions that measures taken against perpetrators will be handled by two different committees (one for students and one for staff).

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring and Evaluation: Yes. Both the Guidelines and the Procedure address monitoring and evaluation.

The Procedure monitors the number of cases, the results of the institutional procedure, the services provided to the victims, outcomes, and the follow-up with victims after a set period of time, as well as other aspects. The work of detecting, handling, and prohibiting discrimination and harassment must be monitored and evaluated in accordance with the Discrimination Act. The document describes a procedure in which an action plan is produced as part of the work of handling a case and that is later evaluated. It states:

'Actions:

The head of the work unit and the head of the department are responsible for ensuring that measures are implemented in accordance with what is stated in the action plan. An action plan can be of a general or specific nature:

General measures to prevent and deter discrimination usually involve the training of staff and informing students and staff of the rules in force. The decision on the actions to be taken should state who is responsible for implementation and how follow-up will take place.

Specific action directed at the person who has subjected someone to discrimination means that the matter with regard to students is referred to the disciplinary committee and to the personnel

responsibility committee in the case of an employee. The Disciplinary Board may decide to issue a warning or impose a suspension.

In the event of dissatisfaction with the university's written decisions, measures, or lack of measures, the individual can turn to his / her trade union and / or to the Discrimination Ombudsman, who can then represent a person in court.

Follow-up and closure of the case: It is important that there is follow-up to the action plan. As an employer and education provider, the university has the obligation to follow up on the case and ensure that the harassment has ceased. The head of the work unit and the head of the department have the responsibility to follow up on the measures implemented and to evaluate them and to monitor the situation / work climate by watching for continued or new signs of misconduct. Particular attention should be paid to the victim. The responsible managers must organise and carry out several follow-up interviews.'

The Guidelines monitor the number of cases, the results of the institutional procedure, and outcomes. According to the Work Environment Act (AML) and regulation AFS 2001: '1) the university has the responsibility and duty to conduct systematic work environment management as a natural part of its activities.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

The Procedure sets out a step-by-step procedure for reporting and investigating cases of violence among students and staff.

The Procedure policy defines: Who to contact, how to report, the description of the investigation, a time frame, responsible persons/units, outcomes, and sanctions.

Who to contact: A lawyer / investigator, HR director, HR specialist, someone whom the person reporting has confidence in (for example, manager, responsible teacher).

How to report: Anyone who claims to have experienced harassment, sexual harassment, retaliation, or any other form of discrimination can report it. Such misconduct can also be reported by a third party who has witnessed it. A report, in oral or written form, can be submitted to the persons listed above under 'who to contact'.

The contact persons are in turn responsible for forwarding the application to the registrar after having written down the application and had it approved by the person who wants to register.

The report must contain an account of what happened, when and where it happened, who was involved, and in what way any such individuals were involved, as well as information about any witnesses. A form for submitting a report can be found at: www.hv.se/likavillkor.

Reports can also be sent directly to the registrar at University West, either via e-mail or by post.

When a report is received, the receiving party informs the responsible manager and work unit manager, who are responsible for the ensuing investigation and any measures taken. The report must be recorded and documented in writing.

The Discrimination Act also contains a ban on retaliation (Chapter 2, § 18). In the first instance, these are punitive measures designed to protect the person who reported or pointed out that the employer / education provider violates the Discrimination Act.

Apart from reporting to University West, anyone who is a member of a trade union / student union can also contact their organisation for support and help. Union representatives can also help with reporting directly to the discrimination ombudsman (DO).

If the case concerns discrimination, harassment, or sexual harassment that is related to any of the grounds for discrimination, gender, transgender identity or expression, ethnicity, religion or other belief, disability, sexual orientation or age, the report can be submitted directly to the DO.² In such cases, University West will be given the opportunity to submit an opinion to the DO and submit its views on the matter.

Confidentiality and documentation: A report of suspected discrimination, harassment, or sexual harassment is to be regarded as a public document received by the university. The case will therefore be registered with the registrar.

Responsible persons/units: Responsible manager and work unit manager.

Description of the investigation: Once the university has received a report, the matter is handled by the relevant work unit (i.e. the respective department or the administration or library).

The persons who receive the report inform the relevant work unit (head of department and head of work unit) and the person responsible for the investigation is the head of the given work unit, i.e. the head of department / library director / university director (they are supported by their HR partner). An advisory group is convened if necessary, which is made up of investigators (lawyers) at the level of the administration and the HR equality specialist, as well as other experts who are deemed necessary in the investigation work (e.g. occupational health care). The head of the work unit informs the rector.

The investigators (lawyers) and the advisory group (if there is one) inform everyone involved and the affected managers on how the case should be handled and start an investigation. Those involved are informed of available support functions. The chief safety representative is informed.

The investigator (lawyer) carries out the investigation. The investigation is carried out promptly, objectively, legally, and with respect for everyone involved and with the discretion that the situation requires. Those involved are heard, and what emerges during the investigation and is found important for the case is communicated to the interested parties, who are given the opportunity to comment. The affected managers are kept continuously informed.

The investigation is documented in writing and the results of the investigation are also recorded and reported in writing.

During the course of the investigation, it may be necessary to take ongoing measures to prevent the discrimination from continuing. The respective work unit manager is responsible for ensuring that such measures are implemented with support and recommendations from the advisory group.

Outcomes / Sanctions: When the investigation is completed, the investigator prepares a proposal for a decision on the case under investigation. Decisions are made regardless of the types of sanctions imposed and measures that are implemented. Who makes the decision depends on who / what the decision concerns. The head of the work unit, with support and recommendations from the investigator and advisory group, makes decisions in cases where an employee is suspected of subjecting a student to discrimination, harassment, or sexual harassment. If discrimination, harassment, or sexual harassment is found to have occurred, the vice chancellor decides whether

² www.do.se

the matter should be referred to the Personnel Liability Committee. The HR manager then prepares and presents the matter to the Personnel Liability Committee.

The disciplinary sanctions that can be applied include a warning and a salary deduction. In the case of more serious incidents, termination or dismissal may be considered. Cases concerning a student who subjects another student or employee at the university to harassment described in Chapter 1, Section 4 of the Discrimination Act (2008: 567) may, if there is a well-founded suspicion of such an incident, be reported to the rector for further investigation as a disciplinary matter. The Disciplinary Board decides on disciplinary measures against students. The disciplinary sanctions that can be applied include a warning or a suspension. If applicable, the union representative is informed. Decisions must be recorded and decisions as well as decision documents are archived with the registrar. The written decision must also report on the measures that have been taken / will be taken, and this is done in the form of an action plan. An action plan describes what has emerged in the investigation and the analysis that has been made. The action plan must clearly state what is to be done, who is responsible for doing it/ensuring it is done, and when it is to be done (schedule). It also needs to be clear how the follow-up to the action plan will be done (who is responsible for the follow-up, when, and how). The action plan also needs to state what University West is doing to prevent similar incidents from happening and what measures are being taken. When a decision has been made, the decision and the basis for the decision are submitted to the registrar.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Anne-Charlott Callerstig in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

